

HEAT TRANSFER VIA AN AIRFOIL HEAT EXCHANGER IN A FLOW WITH PERIODIC TEMPERATURE CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

An airfoil heat exchanger (HEX) is an airfoil with several inner channels in which a heat transport medium (HTM) flows. Various airfoil heat exchangers are connected by tubes, wherein the HTM flows from the hot to cold sections for heat transport. If stators or guide vanes in a turbofan are modified to become airfoil heat exchangers, lightweight and compact intercooling and recuperating systems can be installed into turbofans. In this study, using a thermofluid analysis validated through experiments, heat transfer via an airfoil heat exchanger in a flow with periodic temperature change was numerically investigated. When the frequency of periodic temperature change is 5000 Hz, the space average heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces has a 10% higher value than that at steady state. When the phase lag between the airfoil HEX temperature and air temperature with periodic change is maximum, the heat flux through the all airfoil HEX surfaces is also maximum because of the heat capacity of the airfoil HEX.

INTRODUCTION

Intercooled and recuperated (ICR) turbofans, as well as geared turbofans and open rotors, have the great potential to reduce fuel burn in aviation. ICR gas turbines can also be used for turbo-electric hybrid propulsors as power generators. An intercooler is generally located between low-pressure and high-pressure compressors in a multi-stage compression system. The intercooler, which is generally cooled by cold bypass air, lowers the temperature, increases the density, and decreases the volume flow rate of air passing through the high-pressure compressor, thus reducing its compression work and enhancing thrust. However, the intercooler also lowers the temperature of air at the inlet of a combustor, thus

augmenting the specific fuel consumption (SFC). By contrast, a recuperator is generally located between a high-pressure compressor and a combustor, and it is heated by a hot exhaust gas. The recuperator increases the temperature at the inlet of a combustor, thus reducing the SFC. However, the recuperator also absorbs heat from the exhaust gas, thus reducing the thrust. Here, an ICR, i.e., the combination of an intercooler and a recuperator, is used, thus simultaneously lowering the SFC and increasing the thrust. Because of this, ICR gas turbines have been extensively used as industrial gas turbines.

However, there are no ICR turbofans because conventional concepts of ICR turbofans are too heavy for use as aviation propulsors. When an airplane flies at constant attitude, constant altitude, and constant Mach number, the lift force balances the weight and the drag force balances the thrust. In addition, the ratio of the lift force to the drag force (L/D) acting on the airplane is constant in that case. Therefore, additional thrust, namely additional fuel, is required for flight when the airplane mass increases owing to installation of ICR systems. The condition to reduce the fuel burn of an airplane whose body mass is M [kg] is as follows:

$$\Delta m < \frac{M + m}{\mu} \frac{\Delta S_{FC}}{S_{FC} - \Delta S_{FC}} \quad (1)$$

where engines mass m [kg] increases by Δm [kg] and S_{FC} [kg/(s·N)] reduces by ΔS_{FC} [kg/(s·N)] owing to installation of ICR systems. μ is an impact factor against the entire airplane mass, including reinforcement members, to support engines when the engines' masses change. Conventional concepts of ICR turbofans use heavy metallic heat exchangers as well as long and heavy air ducts connected from the original places to the heat exchangers and from the heat exchangers back to the original places [1]. The conventional concepts of ICR

turbofans do not obey equation (1); this is the reason why there are no ICR turbofan concepts. To design ICR turbofans following equation (1), lightweight and compact ICR systems are definitely required. Ito proposed a new ICR aviation gas turbine as shown in Fig. 1, wherein the lightweight and compact ICR systems were installed [2]. The systems use existing stators or vanes in an aviation gas turbine as heat transfer surfaces, which are called ‘airfoil heat exchangers’ [3]. A couple of airfoil heat exchangers are connected by tubes, in which a heat transport medium (HTM) flows as shown in Fig. 2. The HTM connecting tubes require a much smaller diameter than the air ducts for the conventional ICR aviation gas turbines; therefore, additional weight can be minimized. In addition, the working airflow path can remain in the same position as a baseline gas turbine. Therefore, there is no additional pressure loss. In the intercooling system, heat exchanger A works as an air cooler, and heat exchanger B works as a radiator. Conversely, in the recuperating system, heat exchanger A works as a heat absorber, and heat exchanger B works as an air heater.

A cascade of airfoil heat exchangers is physically similar to a cascade of conventional fluid-cooled turbine blades without film cooling although the cascade of turbine blades is not a heat exchanger. Heat transfer of airfoils in a high-speed compressible flow has been studied since the 1940s. Johnson and Rubesin [4] organized correlations between the outlet Reynolds number and Nusselt number that were derived for a plane in a range of boundary layer conditions from a fully laminar to a fully turbulent flow. Ainley [5], Fray and Barnes [6], Hodge [7], Wilson and Pope [8], Andrews and Bradley [9] and Turner [10] summarized the correlations for a cascade of turbine blades with air internal cooling in a steady high-speed compressible flow. Freche and Diaguila [11] reported the correlation for a cascade of turbine blades with liquid internal cooling. Within gas turbines, the flow is affected by periodic unsteady wakes because of the interaction between the rotor and stator. The effect of periodic unsteady wake flows on heat transfer of turbine blades has been studied by Dunn [12], Wittig et al. [13], Dullenkopf et al. [14] and Han et al. [15]. They noted that periodic unsteady wakes enhance heat transfer performance. In addition, they mentioned that the higher frequency of passing wakes results in a higher heat transfer.

The unsteady wakes are velocity defects caused by a blockage and the drag of each blade; however, they are also due to the total temperature lowness effect caused by each cooled blade. Conventional studies have not clearly distinguished between the wake effects caused by the velocity defect effect and temperature lowness effect. Recently, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was used to analyse the boundary layer development, boundary layer transition, and heat transfer from a high-speed compressible flow to solid surfaces with sufficient accuracy. In this study, a CFD code validated by wind tunnel tests [16] was used to investigate the effect of flows with a periodic temperature change on heat transfer via airfoil heat exchangers.

Fig. 1 New intercooled and recuperated (ICR) aviation gas turbine

Fig. 2 Airfoil heat exchanger system using heat transport medium (HTM) between a hot and cold sections

Fig. 3 Calculation mesh for the diffusing cascade of airfoil heat exchangers

THERMOFLUID ANALYSIS METHOD

ANSYS Fluent 16.0 was employed as a thermofluid analysis tool, and a two-dimensional calculation was conducted. Figure 3 shows the simulated domains with

calculation meshes. In this study, three types of calculation meshes were prepared.

The first type of mesh was used for validating the fluid analysis compared with experimental results of Westphal and Godwin [18]. In addition, this type of mesh was used for numerical simulation of a cascade of adiabatic airfoils in the chapters AIRFOIL THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY EFFECT and PERIODIC TEMPERATURE CHANGE EFFECT. In this type, the only domain of compressible airflow outside the airfoil heat exchanger was used for the analysis. This type of mesh featured 85,258 elements.

The second type of mesh was used to validate the thermofluid analysis compared with our wind tunnel test. In this type, the calculation mesh corresponded to the real structure of the centre airfoil heat exchanger used for the wind tunnel tests as shown in Fig. 4. The centre airfoil heat exchanger consisted of the airfoil heat exchanger body, made of stainless steel, five HTM tubes, and adhesive regions, with a gap thickness of $\delta_{\text{gap}} = 0.05$ mm between the five HTM tubes and the airfoil heat exchanger body. The equivalent thermal conductivity of the adhesive regions is as mentioned in the chapter EXPERIMENTS FOR VALIDATION. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 3(b), the four simulated domains were as follows: one for the compressible airflow outside of the airfoil heat exchanger with 85,258 elements, one for the airfoil heat exchanger body with 44,712 elements, one for the five HTM tubes with 11,930 elements, and one for the adhesive regions with 3,764 elements.

The third type of mesh was used for the discussion of heat transfer via a cascade of airfoil heat exchangers in a flow with periodic temperature change. In this type of mesh, the calculation mesh corresponded to the ideal structure of the airfoil heat exchangers used for a practical gas turbine. The materials of the airfoil heat exchanger were three: stainless steel (SUS), ceramic-matrix composite (CMC), and aluminium in the chapters of AIRFOIL THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY EFFECT and PERIODIC TEMPERATURE CHANGE EFFECT. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 3(c), the two simulated domains were as follows: one for the compressible airflow outside of the airfoil heat exchanger with 85,258 elements, and one for the airfoil heat exchanger body with 29,198 elements.

For the compressible airflow, the density-based Roe-FDS scheme and the γ - Re_{th} laminar-turbulent transition model for a low Reynolds number type were employed. Interpolation methods were 2nd-order upwind for the density, momentum, and energy equations and 1st-order upwind for the four turbulent equations. Calculations were regarded as convergent when all residual errors were less than 10^{-5} . In the boundary layer regions on the outer surfaces of the airfoil heat exchanger, sufficiently thin meshes in the normal direction were provided at $y^+ \sim 1$ for the γ - Re_{th} laminar-turbulent transition model for a low Reynolds number type; the number of meshes in the flow direction were 1,000 points on the airfoil surface. According to a previous study [17], $\text{Re}_{\text{th}} = 50$ is the best

choice for determining the transition point from a laminar to turbulent boundary layer on each airfoil heat exchanger.

The total pressure was fixed as the inlet boundary condition, and the static pressure was fixed as the outlet boundary condition of the compressible airflow.

The total temperature T_{tot} at the inlet boundary was temporally set as

$$T_{\text{tot}} = T_{\text{tot,ave}} + \Delta T_{\text{tot}} \sin[2\pi ft] \quad (2)$$

where $T_{\text{tot,ave}}$, ΔT_{tot} , and f are the time average, amplitude, and frequency of the periodic inlet total temperature, respectively; t is the elapsed time.

The heat transfer coefficient h_{htm} and the HTM temperature were fixed as the boundary conditions of the inner surfaces of the five HTM tubes. According to a previous study [17], $h_{\text{htm}} = 20,000$ was used based on the Dittus–Boelter correlation.

$$q = h_{\text{htm}} [T_{\text{htm}} - T_i] \quad (3)$$

where T_i was the local solid temperature in mesh i of the tube surface that was in contact with the heat transport medium. T_{htm} was the heat transport medium temperature.

All other contact boundary conditions between the two domains were set as stationary surfaces with no temperature difference between the two connected domains.

EXPERIMENTS FOR VALIDATION

First, to validate the above method of fluid analysis for compressible airflow outside of the airfoil heat exchanger, the experimental results by Westphal and Godwin [18] were used. They deployed a cascade of NACA 65-(12)10 in a wind tunnel. We chose the experimental result at solidity σ of 1.5, an attack angle α of 14.9° , and a stagger angle β of 45° .

Second, to validate our thermofluid analysis for airfoil heat exchangers, we performed wind tunnel tests as follows. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no wind tunnel tests for this type of airfoil heat exchangers.

A closed-return wind tunnel was employed at Tokyo Institute of Technology to produce a subsonic airflow. The cross-sectional size of the test section was 60×30 mm. Its Mach number capabilities ranged from 0 to 0.8, and Mach numbers ranging from 0.4 to 0.5 were chosen for testing the airfoil heat exchangers in an aviation gas turbine associated with an inverter (Fuji Electric. FRN30F1S-2J). The Mach number was controlled at an arbitrary value by an inverter-controlled roots blower (ANLET BE125H).

Fig. 4 Diffusing cascade of airfoil heat exchangers: $L_C = 44$ mm, $\sigma = 1.5$, $\alpha = 14.9^\circ$, and $\beta = 45^\circ$

The roots blower generated a sufficiently turbulent inlet airflow, and the generated airflow involved no wakes from preceding airfoils, unlike the airflow observed in a practical axial gas turbine. The turbulent intensity of the airflow at the inlet of the centre airfoil heat exchanger was 4.0%, as measured by a hot-wire probe with a 5 μm tungsten wire.

NACA 65-(12)10 airfoils with five inner HTM channels were employed as airfoil heat exchangers. The airfoil bodies were made of SUS304 because of its thermal conductivity of $\sim 16 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$ is similar to that of titanium alloy. The chord length, L_c , was 44.0 mm, and the width was 28 mm. The outer shape of the airfoil was formed by a wire electric discharge machine. The arithmetic average of the surface roughness on the pressure side was 0.52 μm , and that on the suction side was 1.43 μm . The airfoil heat exchangers were deployed at the same positions as those tested by Westphal and Godwin [18], namely at a solidity σ of 1.5, an attack angle α of 14.9° , and a stagger angle β of 45° .

Twelve K-type thermocouples with a diameter of 0.5 mm were installed to measure the temperature distribution of the centre airfoil heat exchanger. All thermocouples T_1 to T_{12} were located at the airfoil mid-span. In this study, the potential differences between the reference thermocouple T_1 and one of the other thermocouples were measured directly. This measurement method enhanced the accuracy of the temperature differences detection up to less than 1 K. To calibrate the thermocouples, and considering the digital voltage meter error, all thermocouple tips were placed in ice water at a constant temperature of 273.15 K. We developed a PC-based data acquisition software program to cancel out temperature drifts from the target temperature of 273.15 K. Therefore, an accuracy of $\pm 0.025 \text{ K}$ was achieved for the temperature differences recorded for all thermocouples.

The HTM flowed inside the five serially connected stainless steel tubes in the centre airfoil heat exchanger with U-turn sections from the trailing to the leading edges. The HTM flowrate was controlled by a recirculation pump driven by an inverter-controlled AC motor. The HTM temperature was controlled by a cooler section submersed in a cooling thermostatic bath maintained at an arbitrary temperature with an accuracy of 0.1 K. Pressure was maintained at 10 MPa by using a plunger pump to draw the HTM into the flow loop.

The five stainless steel tubes and the airfoil heat exchanger were bonded by thermally conductive adhesive with a thermal conductivity of $15 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$. An ideal condition for the adhesive regions was that the thermally conductive adhesive completely filled each gap between the five HTM tubes and the airfoil heat exchanger body. Unfortunately, some parts of each gap were filled by air instead of the adhesive. The average thermal conductivity was evaluated at $0.07 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$ of k_{adh} by the preliminary experiments.

Two thermocouples were installed to measure HTM temperature, one upstream and one downstream with respect to the centre airfoil heat exchanger. The potential difference between the thermocouples was also measured

directly to calculate the heat flowrate from the hot airflow to the cold HTM flowing through the centre airfoil heat exchanger.

VALIDATION OF THERMOFLUID ANALYSIS BY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

First, to validate that the most difficult numerical methods of the compressible airflow were suitable for the target flow field, pressure distribution on the outer shape of the airfoil heat exchanger was compared to the conventional experimental data by Westphal and Godwin [18], as mentioned in the previous chapter. Figure 5(a) shows a comparison of pressure distributions around the airfoil between experimental results obtained by Westphal and Godwin [18] and the fluid analysis results at 0.52 of inlet Mach numbers. Although there were some differences, a quantitative agreement was achieved by using the above method of fluid analysis of the compressible airflow domain.

Second, to validate the above method of thermofluid analysis for an airfoil heat exchanger by experimental results, the calculation mesh as shown in Fig. 3(b) was prepared, and all boundary conditions were set the same for the validation experiments. Figure 5(b) shows a comparison of solid temperatures experimentally measured by the twelve thermocouples with solid temperatures at corresponding positions numerically obtained. The

(a) Comparison of pressure distribution on outer surfaces of airfoil

(b) Comparison of temperature distribution in the centre of airfoil heat exchanger

Fig. 5 Validation of method of thermofluid analysis for an airfoil heat exchanger by wind tunnel tests results

following experimental and numerical conditions were set: a chord length of 44 mm for the airfoil heat exchanger, an angle of attack of 14.9° , a stagger angle of 45° , a solidity of 1.5 for the cascade of the airfoil heat exchangers, a temperature of 330 K for the inlet air, a temperature of 310 K for the inlet HTM, an airflow rate corresponding to the defined Reynolds number, and an HTM flow rate corresponding to 0.30 of the heat capacity flow rates ratio. Then, the solid temperatures at the twelve thermocouples were uniquely obtained. The maximum error of the differences between experimental and numerical solid temperatures was 1.3 K, and the average error was 0.51 K.

AIRFOIL THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY EFFECT

Before investigations of the periodic temperature change effect on heat transfer, the thermal conductivity effect of airfoil materials on heat transfer should be studied. Here, the most common materials used for airfoil HEXs were considered. The first material was stainless steel, whose thermal conductivity k is $16 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$. This is because we used stainless steel for the wind tunnel test in the validation mentioned before. In addition, its thermal conductivity is almost the same as those of the materials used for practical compressors or vanes; for example, approximately $20 \text{ W/K}\cdot\text{m}$ for titanium alloy and $11\text{--}21 \text{ W/K}\cdot\text{m}$ for nickel-based heat-resistant alloy. The second one was aluminium, whose thermal conductivity k is $202 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$. This is because aluminium is a typical and traditional material used for heat exchanger. Furthermore, it is convenient to investigate the thermal conductivity effect of airfoil materials on heat transfer because its thermal conductivity is almost ten times higher than that of stainless steel. The third one was ceramic-matrix composite (CMC), whose thermal conductivity k is $60 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$. This is a next-generation heat-resistant and lightweight material alternative to heavy nickel-based heat-resistant alloy.

In cases of steady states, Fig. 6 shows static temperature distributions for four airfoil conditions: (a) an adiabatic airfoil with k of $0 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, (b) airfoil HEX made of stainless steel with k of $16 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, (c) airfoil HEX made of CMC with k of $60 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, and (d) airfoil HEX made of aluminium with k of $202 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$. Each figure in Fig. 6 shows the static temperature distribution around a cascade of three airfoils. For easy comprehension, the upper channel is painted with a colour interval of 10 K, the middle channel is painted with a colour interval of 1 K, and the lower channel is represented by contour lines with an interval of 1 K. Figure 7 shows the total temperature distribution in the case of a steady state on the airfoil HEX surface made of aluminium with k of $202 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, which corresponds to the condition in Fig. 6 (d).

As shown in Figs. 6 and 7, heat transfer mechanism is as follows:

1: Compressible air around the airfoil HEX decreases in the boundary layers on the airfoil HEX surfaces. Here, momentum energy is converted into thermal energy. Then,

(a) On the adiabatic airfoil: $k = 0 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$

(b) On the airfoil HEX with k of $16 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$

(c) On the airfoil HEX with k of $60 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$

(d) On the airfoil HEX with k of $202 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$

Fig. 6 Static temperature distribution for steady state cases (The colour intervals are 10 K, 1 K, and 1 K for the upper, the middle, and the lower channels, respectively)

Fig. 7 Total temperature distribution on the airfoil HEX with k of $202 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$ for steady state cases (The colour intervals are 10 K, 1 K, and 1 K for the upper, the middle, and the lower channels, respectively)

Fig. 8 Static temperature distribution for cases with a periodic total temperature with a frequency of 1000 Hz (The colour intervals are 10 K, 1 K, and 1 K for the upper, the middle, and the lower channels, respectively)

Fig. 9 Thermal conductivity effect on average heat flux through the airfoil HEX surfaces

the static temperature in the boundary layers increases.

2: The static temperature in the boundary layers is higher than that on the surfaces of the airfoil HEX internally cooled by cold HTM. Therefore, thermal energy is transmitted from the boundary layers to the airfoil HEX.

3: The total temperature in the boundary layers, which represents the total energy of air, decreases. It means hot compressible airflow is cooled by the cold airfoil HEX.

With an increase in thermal conductivity k , the temperatures at both ends of the airfoil HEX decrease because of good heat conduction. Then temperature difference between the local air temperature and local airfoil temperature increases, and the heat transfer rate increases. The space average heat fluxes through all the airfoil HEX surfaces were (a) 0 W/m², (b) 19.287 kW/m², (c) 23.033 kW/m², and (d) 25.590 kW/m².

Next, heat transfer in a flow with periodic temperature changes was considered. Differently from the steady states, the temperature distribution around the airfoil HEX and heat transfer rate temporally changed. Figure 8 shows the static temperature distributions at maximum heat transfer rate from the hot air to the cold airfoil HEX with k of 0, 16, 60 and 202 W/(m·K). The maximum heat transfer rate can be obtained when the highest temperature is located close to the airfoil HEX.

Figure 9 shows the tendencies of the time and space average heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces with changes in thermal conductivity k . As mentioned above, heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces increases with an increase in thermal conductivity k . In addition, there are no differences between heat fluxes at steady state and those at periodic temperature changes at low thermal conductivity k . However, the differences were pronounced at high thermal conductivity k . At $k = 202$ W/(m·K), the heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces at periodic temperature changes increased by 2.2% compared with that at steady state. Therefore, the periodic temperature change effect on heat transfer will be considered in the next chapter by comparing the results of an airfoil HEX made of aluminium with $k = 202$ W/(m·K).

PERIODIC TEMPERATURE CHANGE EFFECT

In cases of airfoil HEX surfaces made of aluminium with k of 202 W/(m·K), Fig. 10 shows static temperature distributions for four conditions of periodic temperature change; (a) steady state with f of 0 Hz, (b) periodic temperature change with f of 1000 Hz, (c) periodic temperature change with f of 5000 Hz, and (d) periodic temperature change with f of 10000 Hz. Because the chord length of the airfoil HEX was 44 mm and the average airflow velocity was 240 m/s, it took 0.000183 s for the air to pass through the airfoil HEX. Therefore, the cycle lengths of the periodic temperature change were about 5.5 times for 1000 Hz, 1.1 times for 5000 Hz, and 0.55 time for 10000 Hz against the chord length of the airfoil HEX as shown in Fig. 10.

Here, Fig. 11 compares the time and space average heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces with changes in frequency of the periodic temperature change f . The time and space average heat flux through the all airfoil

Fig. 10 Static temperature distribution in cases of periodic total temperature with various frequencies (the colour intervals are 10 K, 1 K, and 1 K for the upper, middle, and lower channels, respectively)

HEX surfaces were (a) 25.590 kW/m², (b) 26.164 kW/m², (c) 28.189 kW/m², and (d) 25.813 kW/m². The heat flux at $f = 5000$ Hz was 10.1% higher than that at steady state.

The reason why the heat flux at $f = 5000$ Hz was the highest will be discussed. Figure 12 shows the temporal change in the space average heat flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces with a change in the frequency of the periodic temperature change f . The horizontal axis is dimensionless time $1/f$. Its zero point corresponds to the point where the highest total temperature reaches the centre of the airfoil HEX. The upper three curves are the

Fig. 11 Thermal conductivity effect on average heat flux through the airfoil HEX surfaces

Fig. 12 Phases of each airfoil HEX against the temperature difference between HTM and air at the centre of airfoil HEX

space average heat fluxes through all the airfoil HEX surfaces for $f = 1000$ Hz, 5000 Hz, and 10000 Hz. The points where the vertical short lines cut the above three curves correspond to the maximum values of the above three curves. The lower solid curve is the temperature difference between the HTM temperature and the total temperature of the air at the centre of the airfoil HEX. As shown in Fig. 12, there are phase lags between the upper three curves and the lower curve. When the lower curve has a maximum value, the temperature difference between air and HTM is maximum. When the upper three curves have maximum values, the temperature difference between air and the airfoil HEX surfaces is maximum. The upper and lower curves have different phases. This is because the airfoil HEX has a heat capacity. The phase delay causes the space average temperature difference between air and the airfoil HEX surfaces increases. As shown in Fig. 3, the phase of the space average heat flux at $f = 5000$ Hz is the most delayed; therefore the space average heat flux at $f = 5000$ Hz has the highest value.

CONCLUSION

In this study, using a thermofluid analysis validated by experiments, heat transfer via an airfoil heat exchanger in a flow with periodic temperature change was numerically investigated. When the frequency of the periodic temperature change was 5000 Hz, the space average heat

flux through all the airfoil HEX surfaces was 10% higher value than that at steady state. When the phase lag between the airfoil HEX temperature and the air temperature with a periodic change was a maximum, heat flux through the all airfoil HEX surfaces was a maximum because of the heat capacity of the airfoil HEX.

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